

ISic1289

I.Sicily inscription 1289

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Ἀφρο]δισίας καὶ
2. [Θε]υδᾶ καὶ Μαρύλλας
3. εἰς μνεῖαν γονέων
4. τέκνα ἐποίησαν

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491451

EDCS 39101658

PHI 140779

PHI 175600

Bibliography

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